

MULTI-PHYSICS SIMULATION OF SOFT MAGNETIC COMPOSITES FOR INDUCTIVE POWER TRANSFER SYSTEMS

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ABSTRACT

Inductive power transfer (IPT) systems have been studied and developed as one of the methods for wireless electric vehicle charging. Typical IPT wireless charging systems utilize ferrite as a magnetic material for improving power transfer efficiency, but the brittle characteristics of ferrite limit its application within IPT systems that will carry mechanical loading. Soft Magnetic Composites (SMCs) are composed of a ferromagnetic filler in an electrically insulating matrix. In this research, SMCs allow new designs of IPT systems based on optimized structural performance, thermal properties and power transfer efficiency.

1 INTRODUCTION

Inductive power transfer (IPT) is a method of coupling power across an air gap without any physical contacts, which was proposed more than a century ago [1]. The lack of physical contact allows an IPT system to realize advantages over its conductive counterparts, such as resistance to environmental impacts and convenience. Over time, numerous IPT systems have been developed to utilize these advantages for a wide range of applications, from battery charging, material handling, automatic guided vehicles to bio-medical devices [2]–[6].

One of the more recent developments in IPT systems is wireless charging of electric vehicles (EVs) [7], [8]. For IPT EV charging systems to be economically viable, the pads (consisting of current carrying litz wire coils, ferrite, and a potting mix) placed inside the roadway need to be operational for decades. The practical implementation of an IPT system typically uses ferrite as one type of ferromagnetic material in order to improve magnetic coupling. Ferrite is known to have excellent high-frequency magnetic permeability characteristics and suitable electrical properties, such as low electrical conductivity [9]. Although ferrite is optimal for guiding magnetic field, it might be less practical in applications where large mechanical and thermal stresses are present due to its extreme brittleness. The soft magnetic composite (SMC) in this paper is chosen as a direct replacement to ferrite as the magnetic material. Magment, a composite of cement and ferrite particles, as a SMC is comprised of electrically insulated ferromagnetic particles that generate several worthy advantages when particle size, shape, and microstructure are optimized. This paper focuses on the electromagnetic thermal behavior of an IPT system using either ferrite or an SMC created using the Magment material. A double-D (DD) pad [8] topology was selected as the base comparison. This was initially built using ferrite and energized by an AC current frequency of 85 kHz. The pad's thermal behavior was characterized, compared and validated with simulation. This work is then extended to investigate an identical IPT DD pad topology using a Magment based material in place of ferrite as a direct comparison. The selection and development of a suitable ferromagnetic core composite with multi-functional properties is made, considering installation of IPT pads within a harsh road environment.

2 DOUBLE-D PAD WITH FERRITE

2.1 Experimental setup

An overview of a typical IPT system is shown in Figure 1. In this paper, only the primary side of the IPT system is considered for both simulation and practical validation for simplicity. The primary side consists of a DC power supply connected to an H-bridge driving a DD pad with 60A at 85kHz with LCL compensation.

Figure 1: Overview of a typical IPT system.

- The DD pad considered here as the primary pad of an IPT system consists of a coil made of Litz wire placed on top of eight rectangular bars of ferrite. The enclosure for the pad is a rectangular box sized 230mm x 140mm x 18mm, made of 3D printed ABS to hold the coil and the ferrite together. The DD pad is placed flush with the surface as shown in Figure 2 (b). The box (800mm by 600mm) is filled with a silica sand in this study so the position of the pad can be easily changed. All outer surfaces of the box are insulated using polystyrene walls except the top surface so the thermal simulation only has to consider the thermal loss in only one surface. A thermal camera is placed above the box and one fibre Bragg grating (FBG) sensor is placed inside the centre of the DD pad, to measure temperature.

Figure 2: Dimensions of (a) the DD pad without the casing and (b) DD pad placed inside a box for simulation. All dimensions are in millimeters.

The prototype DD pad built in the laboratory is shown in Figure 3 (a). The experiment setup was established within in an environmental chamber, as shown in Figure 3 (b). During the experiments, the humidity of the environmental chamber was maintained at approximately 20%. The experiments took about six hours to reach steady-state when the pad was flush with the sand surface, and more than half a day when the pad was buried beneath the sand surface.

Figure 3: Photos of (a) the prototype DD pad without the lid before being filled with potting material and (b) the experimental setup around the environmental chamber.

2.2 Multi-physics simulation

All coupled thermal and electromagnetic simulation of IPT pad was conducted in the ANSYS workbench interface. The first step in the simulation program to characterise the material properties such as core and coil loss parameters in electromagnetic simulation; density, specific heat and thermal conductivity in thermal simulation. Table 1 shows the used and measured thermal properties of different materials for thermal simulation.

	Density (g/cm ³)	Specific Heat (J/kgC) *	Isotropic thermal conductivity (W/mC)
3D printed casing	1.02	1536.9	0.137
Polyurethane resin	1.61	1150	0.517
Ferrite	4.6	343.15	4.01
Litz wire	4.8	385	159.5
Sand	1.52	809	0.22

*At ambient temperature

Table 1: Thermal Properties of Experimental Materials

The top surface of the pad is assigned with a temperature dependent convection coefficient, which increases as the temperature of the pad rises. Due to non-linear changes to the properties of air with rising temperature, the increase of the convection coefficient is not linearly proportional to the rise of the pad temperature. The side and bottom surfaces of the box containing the sand and IPT pad are assigned with perfect insulation. Core loss parameters of ferrite N87 can be obtained from the TDL magnetic design tool website [10].

When provided with the initial electrical material properties, the magnetic simulation can calculate the overall power loss in the system when the DD pad is energised. This information is then fed into the thermal simulation, which calculates the rise in temperature that is fed back into the electrical simulation to find new values for power losses in the Litz wire and the ferrite. The iterative cycle of simulations continue until the temperature reaches steady-state within the pad. A flowchart showing the simulation process is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Flowchart of iterative electromagnetic-thermal simulations to find steady-state temperature in the pad during operation.

2.3 Results

Validation of the electromagnetic thermal simulation of the IPT system was conducted using FBG sensor embedded inside the pad and thermal camera. Surface temperature generated by the simulation and the experiment are shown in Figure 5, for an environmental chamber ambient temperature of 50°C.

Figure 5: Surface temperature of DD pad flush with the surface for (a) the simulation and experimental (b) temperature along the line with ambient temperature of 50°C.

As it can be seen from the Figure 5, a very good agreement between results from simulation and experiment were obtained with maximum error less than 7%. The simulation model uses a fully

compacted model of sand without any air inside it, and this introduces some discrepancies in the surface temperature between the simulation and the experiment. The temperature measured by FBG sensors which were placed inside the pad is shown in Figure 6. The experimental results align closely with the simulation results. It is shown that with the rise of ambient temperature, the maximum temperature of the IPT pad increase linearly.

Figure 6: Temperature simulated and measured by the FBG sensor embedded inside the pad against ambient temperature.

Therefore, the ability to predict electromagnetic-thermal performance of an IPT pad embeded inside a box filled with a homogenous material has been demonstrated. The thermal performance of an IPT pad with two configurations including ferrite and SMC magment, has been studied using the developed multi-physics simulation.

3 DOUBLE-D PAD WITH MAGMENT SMC

3.1. Core loss model

While Magment has lower magnetic permeability than ferrite (15-40 vs. $\sim 2,300$ at 85 kHz), this material offers the flexibility to find an optimum set of electromagnetic, mechanical and thermal properties. Indeed, the electromagnetic and thermomechanical properties of Magment can be controlled by tuning the composition, filler/matrix mixing ratio, and size fraction of the magnetic fillers. The electromagnetic performance at low field is encouraging. Figure 7 shows the difference in Quality (Q) factor for similar toroid cores made fully of ferrite, and composites made of 80% crushed equivalent ferrite and 20% Araldite resin and cement Magment, MC40. The quality factor (Q factor) is a ratio between energy stored and dissipated in a system (measured here as the ratio of real over imaginary components of the complex permeability of a toroid inductor). In an IPT pad, a high Q factor is desirable to minimise the power loss. Loss measurements at different temperature, magnetic flux and frequencies are the basis for the electromagnetic model. In future we will iterate, characterise and simulate the developed SMC Magment for DD pad designs to develop an optimised system with similar or improved efficiency to ferrite, but with better mechanical performance. It should be noted that the material utilised in this paper, is not formulated as recommended by the suppliers of Magment.

Figure 7: Comparison of the frequency dependence of Q factor and magnetic permeability (21 °C and <20 mT).

In order to compare the electromagnetic-thermal performance of an IPT pad with different magnetic properties, the amount of power transfer from primary pad to secondary pad (S) is calculated from Equation (1).

$$S = \omega l I^2 k^2 \quad (1)$$

where ω , l , I and k are frequency, inductance, current and coupling coefficient, respectively. Table 2 shows the calculated transferred power from both the ferrite and Magment primary pads, to a ferrite secondary pad at 85 kHz and 60A.

primary-secondary IPT pads	L (μH)	k	S (KVA)
Ferrite - Ferrite	6.51	0.33	1360
Magment - Ferrite	4.66	0.27	653

Table 2: calculated transferred power from primary pad to secondary pad.

As can be seen from Table 2, in order to obtain the same amount of power transfer ($S=1360KVA$) from a Magment primary pad to a Ferrite secondary pad, the current should be increased to 87A (refer to Equation (1)). The calculated total core loss for the Ferrite primary pad is 8.45 W, which is 40% lower than Magment with 11.76W. Figure 8 shows the predicted core loss field for both IPT systems with different magnetic properties.

Figure 8: Core loss field of (a) Magment-Ferrite and (b) Ferrite-Ferrite IPT pads

Figure 9 compares the maximum temperature of the primary pad embedded inside the box, as predicted by the simulation for both ferrite and Magment properties, that transferred the same amount of power to the secondary pad. It is notable that the Magment pad is predicted to experience a maximum coil temperature of 204°C, an increase of 73%, which is due to the rise of coil and core loss by 100% and 40 %, respectively. This indicates a potential thermal concern of using the current Magment based SMC as a replacement of ferrite, to transfer the same amount of power within an IPT system. Therefore, further development of SMCs is required for this application, either based on Magment, or other alternative SMCs such as a composites made from crushed equivalent ferrite.

Figure 9: Comparison of coil temperature of (a) Ferrite and (b) Magment primary pad with considering to transfer the same amount of power to secondary pad at IPT system.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, the electromagnetic thermal performance of an SMC developed for an IPT system is studied. The accuracy of the IPT pad simulation model is found to be within 5%, considering temperatures monitored during experiments completed within an environmental chamber. This demonstrates the ability to model the multi-physics nature of this situation, including electrical, magnetic and thermal behavior of an IPT pad embedded inside a box filled with a homogenous material. The electromagnetic-thermal performance of an SMC material composed of Magment, as an alternative to brittle ferrite within an IPT pad, was studied. It is predicted that the current pad design using the SMC requires higher current for excitation within an IPT system to transfer the same amount of power from primary pad to secondary pad. This results in higher temperatures being generated within the system. Future work is focused on the development and characterisation of SMC materials, and experimental trials to verify performance within an IPT system.

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